

Assessing Water Distribution Network Performance with Customer-oriented Performance Indices.

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Abstract

This study introduces two novel, Customer-oriented Performance Indices (CPIs), which assess water distribution network (WDN) performance based on the duration and severity of pressure deficits. The research used real-world network data and simulated disruptive scenarios to compare the proposed CPIs with existing hydraulic, entropy, and resilience indices. The results show that a highly interconnected, robust network does not guarantee minimum service-level maintenance. The CPIs effectively pinpoint underperforming nodes and quantify the overall system performance of the WDN, facilitating informed decision-making on strategic investments to improve customer service levels. The CPIs are instrumental in identifying critical pipes and the impact of defects on customer satisfaction, enabling water companies to prioritise maintenance efforts and thereby enhance network performance and customer service.

Keywords

Water distribution network (WDN), Customer-oriented Performance Indices (CPIs), Hydraulic Performance, and Performance Indices.

Highlights

- WDN performance is investigated using new Customer-oriented Performance Indices (CPIs).
- New CPIs can be used to locate areas/nodes in WDNs with poor customer levels of service.
- The CPIs could help utilities focus investment on improving the service level.

Introduction

Water distribution networks (WDNs) are essential for urban infrastructure, providing reliable access to sufficient water to meet daily user demand. However, due to global population growth, rapid urbanisation, industrialisation, and rising customer expectations, water demand has surged, placing additional strain on existing infrastructure (Huzsvar et al., 2021). The ageing of WDNs and increased consumer expectations have placed immense strain on systems, leading to performance issues like frequent leaks and pressure deficits (Al-Barqawi & Zayed, 2006). The impact of defects in WDNs on hydraulic performance can vary, necessitating strategic operational and management approaches. Blockages, for instance, reroute water flow, requiring greater capacity to sustain pressure in downstream nodes. Additionally, defects that increase pipe roughness or reduce pipe diameter can decrease flow capacity and induce energy dissipation, leading to pressure shortfalls. The efficient and effective operation of water distribution networks is crucial to providing high-quality services to customers. As water demand and customer expectations increase, authorities expect high-quality services from water utilities. To meet these expectations while managing costs, utilities strive to enhance their services and improve water distribution infrastructure through innovation. In England and Wales, water utilities invested over £8 billion between 2019 and 2020 to enhance the services from water and sewerage systems (Water UK, 2019). Water main breaks are a significant issue in the United States, with an estimated 240,000 occurrences annually. These leaks cost \$2.6 billion per year. Access to reliable and safe water is vital for households, hospitals, schools, factories, and farms, impacting various economic activities (Colin, 2011). According to the American Society of Civil Engineers (2013), deteriorating water infrastructure will cost households \$59 billion from 2013 to 2020, while businesses will face a higher cost of \$147 billion.

Customer satisfaction is paramount in water distribution networks (WDNs), guiding the design and operational policies to ensure service quality under all circumstances. To achieve this, utilities employ decision-support tools, such as performance indices, to monitor and measure WDN performance, thereby enhancing supply continuity and operational efficiency (Muranho et al., 2014).

Performance evaluation in water and wastewater utilities typically involves two methods: systems of performance indices and technical performance assessment tools (Cardoso et al., 2004). The selection of performance indices should be customised to align with specific assessment objectives. These indices must be flexible and interpretable, enabling utilities to adapt and make informed decisions for effective network management and improved service quality (Muranho et al., 2014). Technical performance assessment varies among authors, depending on the study's objectives, which include evaluating water supply reliability, structural robustness, redundancy, and connectivity using hydraulic, entropy, and resilience indices (Fujiwara & De Silva, 1990; Awumah et al., 1990; Ostfeld, 2002).

Hydraulic reliability provides a more comprehensive perspective on the performance of the water distribution network (WDN). This concept centres on the capability of the WDN to meet user demand (Tanyimboh & Templeman., 1998; Yazdani et al., 2011). Additionally, resilience reliability has garnered substantial attention in the analysis of WDN performance, with a focus on enhancing the system's robustness against disruptions (Todini, 2000; Prasad & Park, 2004; Jayaram & Srinivasan, 2008; Zhuang et al., 2013). Another crucial aspect is the measurement of entropy reliability, which quantifies the availability of alternative flow paths when a component within the network fails (Awumah & Goulter, 1990; Tanyimboh & Sheahan, 2002). These three facets, hydraulic reliability, resilience reliability, and entropy reliability, together provide a comprehensive approach to understanding and assessing the performance of WDNs, underscoring the importance of robustness, reliability, and user demand satisfaction in ensuring effective water distribution.

In addition, regulatory agencies, like the Office of Water Services (OFWAT) in England and Wales and the American Water Works Association (AWWA) in the US, along with water utilities in their host countries, set performance indices to assess utilities' performance, improving service quality to end-users and protecting the environment (Alegre et al., 2016). However, these indices may not fully capture the user experience from the utility's assets and are focused on the utility's responsiveness in delivering quality service to users. Notably, a robust, redundant WDN does not guarantee that end users receive adequate water throughout the network. Nonetheless, it does ensure the continuity of network operations in the event of unforeseen disruptions. Hence, there needs to be greater clarity between the indices used to measure utility performance and the quality of service experienced by end users.

This study proposes a novel, customer-centric measure of hydraulic performance for water networks that underscores the significance of the end user's experience and highlights critical areas and defects that affect the system's performance. This approach uniquely emphasises the network's capacity to fulfil consumer water quantity demands, intentionally distancing itself from issues of water quality reliability. In this context, we define hydraulic performance as the ability of the system to deliver satisfactory water quantities under all service conditions, with the underlying principle being the provision of adequate pressure.

To fulfil our objectives, we propose the concept of Customer-oriented Performance Indices (CPIs) that evaluate service levels using hydraulic pressure data collected from various nodes in the water distribution network (WDN). The CPIs will offer a detailed analysis of the network's duration and severity of pressure deficits. Consequently, this study will conduct a comparative analysis of the proposed CPIs and existing hydraulic entropy and resilience indices to elucidate the effectiveness of CPIs in gauging user experience and to highlight the shortcomings of existing reliability indices in capturing it. This comparative study will provide utilities with valuable insights into WDN performance that they can use to benchmark their assets against industry standards. This will facilitate a comprehensive evaluation of their service delivery and, in turn, propel significant strides towards improving customer satisfaction.

Methodology

We propose Customer-oriented Performance Indices (CPIs) that assess service levels using time-series pressure data from various water distribution network (WDN) nodes to achieve our objectives. The methodology used in this study utilises the WNTR-EPANET (Klise et al., 2017; Rossman, 2000) library in Python to implement disruptive scenarios and simulate WDN hydraulics. The hydraulic simulation of the network is performed using Pressure-Dependent Demand (PDD), available in WNTR-EPANET, to account for pressure deficiency in the disruptive simulation (Wagner et al., 1988; Wu et al., 2008; Fujiwara & Li, 1998). The network's Customer-oriented Performance Indices (CPIs), hydraulic, resilience, and entropy indices are computed under different disruptive scenarios.

Establishing a system-wide pressure threshold is essential to ensuring the safe and efficient operation of water distribution networks and meeting end-user consumption demands. Pressure-based indices are useful tools for guiding network operation and performance evaluation. One of the primary hydraulic requirements is the minimum pressure requirement. In England and Wales, utilities must maintain a minimum pressure of 10m static head capable of providing nine litres of water per minute, according to Ofwat (2005). However, utilities often design their systems to operate at higher pressure above this standard to mitigate the impact of low pressure during disruptions. This study adopted Yorkshire Water's (2020) minimum water main pressure of 20 meters head outside all properties.

Development of Proposed Customer-Oriented Performance Indices (CPIS)

Applying Yorkshire Water's (2020) minimum water main pressure of 20 meters head at water mains, the following conditions for developing the CPIs are introduced in Eq. (1).

$$\begin{cases} IF & P_j \geq 20 & CPI = 1 \\ IF & P_j < 20 & CPI \neq 1 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

CPI_1 measures the Water Distribution Network's (WDN) reliability in meeting the 20-meter pressure threshold. CPI_1 considers the period of pressure deficits in network nodes throughout the 24-hr simulation period. For node j in the network, the CPI_1 for node j (denoted as $CPI_{1,j}$) is calculated as one minus the ratio of the summed duration of all pressure deficit periods at node j to the total simulation time (T_s). Mathematically, this can be written as:

$$CPI_{1,j} = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n T_{i,j}}{T_s} \quad (2)$$

A pressure deficit period is defined as a period during which the pressure at node j goes below 20 meters. In this equation, $T_{i,j}$ represents the duration of the i^{th} pressure deficit period for node j , n is the total number of deficit periods for node j , and T_s represents the total simulation time. Suppose N is the total number of nodes impacted by pressure deficiency in the network. In that case, the overall performance index is taken as the average performance of individual nodes $CPI_{1,j}$ in the network, denoted as $CPI_{1,Net}$, calculated using Eq. (3) as follows:

$$CPI_{1,Net} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N CPI_{1,j} \quad (3)$$

CPI_2 investigates the WDN's performance based on the severity of pressure deficit over time compared to the 20-meter pressure threshold. It measures this severity by considering the area under the curve of pressure deficit over time. CPI_2 for node j (denoted as $CPI_{2,j}$) is calculated as one minus the ratio of the summed area of the period of all pressure deficit ($A_{i,j}$) at node j to the product of the pressure threshold of 20 m-head and the total simulation time (T_s) and denoted as A_s . Where $A_s = 20T_s$. This product, represented as $A_s = 20T_s$, serves as a reference area. Mathematically, this can be written as:

$$CPI_{2,j} = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n A_{i,j}}{A_s} = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n A_{i,j}}{20T_s} \quad (4)$$

A pressure deficit period is defined as a period during which the pressure at node j goes below 20 meters. Where, $A_{i,j}$ area of the i^{th} pressure deficit for node j , n is the total number of deficit periods for node j , and T_s is the total simulation period and the pressure threshold (20 m- head). Suppose N is the total number of nodes impacted by pressure deficiency in the network. In that case, the overall performance index is taken as the average performance of individual nodes $CPI_{2,j}$ in the network, denoted as $CPI_{2,Net}$, calculated using Eq. (5) as follows:

$$CPI_{2,Net} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N CPI_{2,j} \quad (5)$$

Scenarios

To evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed CPIs, the impact of two common defective scenarios on WDNs' performance is analysed using the proposed CPIs:

Our research methodology evaluates the hydraulic performance of two water distribution networks, Net1 and Net2, under two operational scenarios using Critical Performance Indicators (CPIs). Scenario 1 involves a series of 24-hour hydraulic simulations where individual pipes are sequentially blocked, thereby assessing the number and severity of impacted nodes under different operational conditions. Scenario 2, on the other hand, investigates the effect of a loss in pipe diameter on hydraulic performance. This is achieved through multiple hydraulic simulations in which individual pipe diameters are systematically reduced by varying percentages (10% to 90%) over 24 hours.

To reflect the findings of Boxall et al. (2004), which highlight the importance of roughness and original pipe diameter for calibrating Water Network Distribution (WND) models, the pipe diameters in our study are modified as follows: $D_{effective} = [(D - 2K)]$, where K represents the pipe's current roughness height and D is the original pipe diameter.

In our analysis, Net1 uses pipe diameters ranging from 0.127 to 0.2 meters (5 to 7.9 inches), while Net2 uses diameters between 0.165 and 0.32 meters (6.5 and 12.5 inches). These are commonly used sizes in real-world networks, providing practical insights into the impact of the examined scenarios on network performance. It should be noted that the first single pipes directly connected to the source were excluded from the analysis, as a blockage in these pipes would disconnect the entire network, resulting in zero CPIs. This deliberate exclusion enhances the manageability of our analysis, enabling more focused efforts in addressing low-pressure incidents.

Pipe Criticality Analysis

To highlight the practical utility of our proposed Customer-oriented Performance Indices (CPIs) for identifying pipes with high sensitivity and significant impact on network users, we will employ the pipe criticality indices proposed by Klise et al. (2017). These indices will be used to calculate the number of network nodes affected by each instance of pipe closure. However, it is essential to note that the indices proposed by Klise et al. (2017) have a limitation in capturing the duration and severity of pressure deficit in the network.

To address this limitation and provide a more holistic view of pipe criticality, we will apply our proposed Equations (3) and (5), $CPI_{1,Net}$ and $CPI_{2,Net}$, respectively, in the same analysis. These new indices are designed to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the impact of pipe closure on network performance, as perceived by end users. By integrating these additional indices, we aim to support decision-

making on pipe criticalities, thereby enhancing the network's overall performance and the customer's service experience. Furthermore, to streamline the analysis and ensure practical feasibility, our study will investigate the impact of the first five critical pipes based on the overall network CPIs evaluated.

Water Distribution Network (WDN) Reliability Analysis

Comparative analysis of the network reliability using the proposed CPIs and existing hydraulic indices (Tanyimboh & Templeman, 1998; Yazdani et al., 2011), entropy index (Awumah et al., 1990), and resilience indices (Jayaram & Srinivasan, 2008; Todini, 2000) to elucidate the effectiveness of CPIs in gauging user experience and the shortcomings of the existing metrics in capturing user experience. The hydraulic reliability index proposed by Tanyimboh and Templeman (1998) quantifies a water distribution network's ability to meet user demand under various conditions. It is a function of the network's head-dependent behaviour, reflecting the network's ability to meet a specified minimum pressure head at all demand nodes under all demand and supply conditions. This study takes the minimum required pressure as 20m while the maximum allowable pressure is 60m of static pressure head. Yazdani et al. (2011) used statistical measurements of water distribution networks to analyse robustness and redundancy. They are based on the network's structural patterns and building blocks. Network connectivity was defined as the minimum ratio of demand delivered to the required demand at a node during a pipe-break disruption. Todini's 2000 resilience index for water networks quantifies a system's ability to maintain functionality during disruptions by assessing its capacity to maintain adequate pressure under increased demand or reduced supply conditions. It is computed as the ratio of the total energy supplied by the network to the minimum energy required to satisfy the basic demand, thus providing a measure of the network's excess capacity to manage stress events. The Jayaram and Srinivasan (2008) resilience index for water networks quantifies the system's ability to maintain functionality during disruptions. It computes the surplus power available in the network, defined as the ratio of the total energy supplied by the pumps or sources to the minimum energy required to meet the demand. Awumah et al. (1990) developed an entropy-based index to quantify the redundancy of water distribution networks, which indicates the system's resilience. The index, calculated from the flow distribution across the network's loops, provides a measure of network reliability, with higher entropy values reflecting greater redundancy and, thus, enhanced capacity to oversee disruptions.

The pipe blockage and diameter-reduction scenarios mirror real-world challenges posed by ageing infrastructure and unforeseen disruptions. Such conditions can significantly decrease WDN reliability performance and impact customer experience. By understanding system behaviour under these conditions and by comparing the different reliability indices, utilities can focus maintenance efforts on sensitive pipes. This approach helps prevent significant service disruptions and enhances service delivery reliability, fostering a more customer-oriented approach.

Case Study

To illustrate the practical application of the proposed methodologies, we selected two networks that are representative of typical UK water distribution systems, marked by diversity in pipe sizes, configurations and demand patterns, as case studies. These networks serve as practical contexts for evaluating the effectiveness of our approach, and the characteristics of each network are detailed in Table 1. This real-world application allows for a more nuanced understanding of how the methodologies function under variable conditions, thereby contributing to a more robust and comprehensive evaluation of their potential impact on network reliability.

Table 1. Water Distribution Networks Characteristics.

Network Component	Parameters
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	Net1			Net2		
	25 th	50 th	75 th	25 th	50 th	75 th
Percentile Distribution of Pipe Diameter (m)	0.09	0.1	0.15	0.07	0.1	0.14
Percentile Distribution of Pipe Length (m)	20	39	66	1.9	2.4	10.5
Number of Valves		0			3	
Number of Demand Patterns		10			89	
No. of Pumps		0			0	
No. of Nodes		168			508	
No. of Pipes		175			560	
No. of Tanks		0			1	
No. of Reservoirs		1			1	
Curves		0			1	
Controls		0			69	
Type	Branched			Looped		

Results and Discussions

Table 2 presents the results for Net1 and Net2 in scenario 1, which involves blocking individual pipes and ranking them comparatively between the $CPI_{1,Net}$ and $CPI_{2,Net}$ and hydraulic criticality index by Klise et al. (2017) based on the duration, severity and number of nodes impacted with pressure deficit.

Table 2. Pipe Criticality Analysis based on Customer-Oriented Performance Indices (CPIs) and Klise et al. (2017) for Net1 and Net2.

Pipe Name	Net1			Pipe Name	Net2		
	Number of Impacted Nodes Klise et al. (2017).	$CPI_{1,Net}$	$CPI_{2,Net}$		Number of Impacted Nodes Klise et al. (2017)	$CPI_{1,Net}$	$CPI_{2,Net}$
L07L32MC	103	0.967	0.997	AL-1194	486	0.972	0.983
L07L32MA	102	0.964	0.962	AL-1195	486	0.972	0.984
L07L32MB	101	0.964	0.967	AL-1196	485	0.972	0.984
L07L32LC	62	0.967	0.968	AL-1260	284	0.976	0.987
L07L32LA	61	0.967	0.968	AL-1312	282	0.976	0.988

Table 2, applying $CPI_{1,Net}$ and $CPI_{2,Net}$ facilitates evidence-based decision-making by providing detailed information to rank pipes based on the severity and duration of the pressure deficit at impacted nodes. In the analysis of Net1, we found that although there are no substantial variations in the severity and duration of pressure deficits across the five pipes, pipe-L07L32MA emerged as the most critical, contrary to the Klise et al. (2017) hydraulic index, which identified pipe-L07L32MC as the most critical. Pipe-L07L32MA impacts the pressure deficit at 102 nodes with a $CPI_{1,Net}$ of 0.964 and 0.962 for $CPI_{2,Net}$. According to the Klise et al. (2017) hydraulic index, pipe- L07L32MC appears to be the most critical pipe among the five pipes selected from Net1 in the analysis, with 102 nodes out of 168 experiencing pressure deficits. Given that the pressure deficit can be less severe and of short duration, treating pipe L07L32MC as the most critical pipe may be misleading, since a pipe can affect more nodes less severely for a fleeting period. In comparison, another pipe can affect fewer nodes more severely for a more extended period. Given the complexity of the problem, it is imperative to enrich our analysis with additional information or adopt alternative approaches such as the proposed Critical Performance Indicators (CPIs).

With blockage in pipe-AL-1194 in Net2, the $CPI_{1,Net}$ and $CPI_{2,Net}$ is calculated as 0.972 and 0.983, whereas for pipe-AL-1195, $CPI_{1,Net}$ and $CPI_{2,Net}$ are 0.973 and 0.983. Since the $CPI_{1,Net}$ for pipe-1194 and pipe-AL-1195 are equivalent, indicating both pipes being blocked caused the system to operate below the pressure threshold for an equal amount of time, however, with slightly different severity. We applied the $CPI_{2,Net}$, which indicates that pipe-AL-1194 is the most critical pipe with $CPI_{2,Net}$ of 0.983, as against pipe-AL-1195 of 0.984. Comparatively, for Net2, pipe-AL-1194 and pipe-1195 had an equal number of nodes 486 impacted with pressure deficit when blocked and going by the Klise et al. (2017) hydraulic index, it becomes technically difficult to pinpoint the most sensitive pipe between pipe-AL-1194 and pipe-1195. Consequently, the CPIs provided additional clarity and guidance in selecting the most sensitive pipe.

Furthermore, Table 3 presents the highlighted critical pipes for Net1 and Net2, analysed comparatively between the $CPI_{1,Net}$, $CPI_{2,Net}$ and hydraulics, entropy and resilience indices to reflect on the impact of pressure deficit WDN performance based on users' experience.

Table 3. Comparative Analysis of Net1 and Net2 Performance between CPIs and Hydraulics, Entropy and Resilience Indices, focusing on the Identified Critical Pipes under Blockage and No-blockage conditions.

Network Condition	Hydraulic Indices		Proposed Hydraulic Indices		Entropy Indices	Resilience Indices	
	Minimum Availability Yazdani et al. (2011)	Average Pressure Ratio Tanyimboh, & Templeman (1998)	$CPI_{1,Net}$	$CPI_{2,Net}$	Awumah et al. (1990)	Todini (2000)	Jayaram and Srinivasan (2008)
No Blockage	0.849	1.000	1.00	1.00	0	0.997	0.476
Pipe-L07L32MA Blocked	0.821	1.000	0.964	0.962	0	0.997	0.476
No Blockage	0.805	0.991	0.982	0.991	0.537	0.293	0.082
Pipe-AL-1194 Blocked	0.800	0.991	0.972	0.983	0.732	0.290	0.078

From Table 3, $CPI_{1,Net}$ and $CPI_{2,Net}$, which consider only pressures ≤ 20 m, reveal excellent performance, with all nodes maintaining pressures ≥ 20 m over a 24-hour simulation when there is no blockage in Net1; subsequently, for Net2, the system without blockage in any pipe, some nodes experienced pressure below the required threshold. However, with a blockage in pipe-L07L32MA of Net1, the $CPI_{1,Net}$ and $CPI_{2,Net}$, are 0.964 and 0.962, respectively. Moreover, for Net2, $CPI_{1,Net}$ and $CPI_{2,Net}$ indicate that the blockage in pipe-AL-1194 results in a decrease in overall system performance based on $CPI_{1,Net}$ and $CPI_{2,Net}$, decreasing from 0.982 and 0.991 to 0.972 and 0.983, respectively.

Comparatively, the analysis of Net1 and Net2, as presented in Table 3, reveals that without any pipe blockage, Net1 exhibits a low vulnerability with a minimum availability of 0.849. At the same time, Net2, experiences a marginal shift in the vulnerability index from 0.805 to 0.800 upon blockage in pipe-AL-1194, indicating a slight increase in system vulnerability, reflecting the system's capacity to meet user demand as per (Yazdani et al., 2011) hydraulic index. Also, based on Tanyimboh & Templeman's (1998) hydraulic index, the average pressure ratio of the system is 1.0 and 0.991 for Net1 and Net2, respectively, for both blocked and unblocked critical pipes, indicating that the system operates at a pressure greater than or equal to the 20 m threshold. Although this may not be true, as highlighted by the CPIs for the various nodes due to the critical pipe blockage, it is worth noting that the Tanyimboh & Templeman (1998) approach considers all pressure ranges and nodes with pressure ≥ 20 m, complementing deficit nodes if averaged.

We used Equations (2) and (4) to compute the Critical Performance Indicators (CPIs) for each node during each pipe blockage. As illustrated in Figures 1 and 2, the results reveal the impact of blocked critical pipes in Net1 and Net2, respectively. Both figures exhibit a uniform pattern in the duration ($CPI_{1,j}$) and severity ($CPI_{2,j}$) of pressure deficits. Nevertheless, specific nodes display a noticeable divergence in these indices, indicating varying hydraulic behaviour within the networks. For instance, in Net1, the blockage of pipe L07L32MA resulted in a noteworthy outcome: both the duration and severity of pressure deficits were indexed at approximately 1.0 for $CPI_{1,j}$ and $CPI_{2,j}$, respectively. This signifies a marginal decline in pressure, persisting for a short duration, consistently observed throughout the simulation period.

Figure. 1. Impact of Pipe-L07132MA Blockage on Individual Nodes in Net1

Similarly, from Fig. 2, the closure of a critical pipe, specifically Pipe-AL-1194 in Net2, has demonstrable impacts on the network's hydraulic performance, as evidenced by the changes in the $CPI_{1,j}$ and $CPI_{2,j}$ values for individual nodes in the network. Notably, the recorded CPI values reveal discernible patterns, reflecting the hydraulic disruptions caused by the closure. For instance, some nodes exhibit concurrent changes in $CPI_{1,j}$ and $CPI_{2,j}$, suggesting a direct impact of the pipe closure. In contrast, others show more nuanced variations, indicative of the complex interplay of networks. This analysis underscores the importance of strategic pipe management for maintaining optimal network performance and highlights the utility of CPI indices as sensitive indicators of network performance.

Figure. 2. Impact of Pipe-AL-1194 Blockage on Individual Nodes in Net2

The entropy of Net1, a tree-like network, is zero for both blocked and unblocked critical pipes, indicating a highly deterministic, non-random structure. This zero-entropy value implies a predictable network with no loops, indicating a lack of redundancy. In practice, this implies that any disruption to a single pipe could cause significant service interruptions for downstream nodes due to the absence of alternative water paths, underscoring the network's vulnerability to localised failures. Upon the blockage of critical pipe AL-1194 in Net2, the system's entropy increases, suggesting more unpredictable flow patterns, as shown in Table 3. While

the densely looped network allows water to continue distributing via alternative paths, the Customer-oriented Performance Indices (CPIs) reveal that these paths do not maintain the required pressure at downstream nodes during the blockage, thereby compromising the quality of service for users supplied by those nodes.

The resilience of network Net1, evaluated using indices proposed by Todini (2000) and Jayaram and Srinivasan (2008), remained consistent despite a critical pipe blockage. With resilience indices of 0.997 and 0.476, Net1 demonstrated its ability to maintain water delivery under various conditions, a testament to its inherent redundancy. However, it is essential to note that the local effects of a blockage can be significant, with areas directly served by the blocked pipe potentially experiencing reduced pressure or water outages, and an increase in flow rates and velocities in the remaining pipes. In the Net2 network, the resilience indices decreased slightly when a critical pipe was blocked. The indices changed from 0.293 to 0.082 and from 0.290 to 0.078. This indicates that the network's resilience and ability to handle blockages are slightly lower; nonetheless, the networks continue operation based on built-in redundancies, although customer satisfaction has been affected, as captured in the $CPI_{1,Net}$ and $CPI_{2,Net}$, in Table 3 for blocked and unblocked critical pipes for Net1 and Net2, respectively.

The results for the most critical pipes in Net1 and Net2 (Table 4) illustrate the impact of diameter reduction on system performance in several reliability indices.

Table 4. Comparative Analysis of the Impact of the Combined Effect of Roughness and Loss in Diameter on the Performance of Net1 and Net2 Water Distribution Networks (Scenarios 2)

Pipe Name	Condition	Hydraulic Indices		Proposed Hydraulic Indices		Entropy Indices	Resilience Indices	
	Reductions (%)	Minimum Availability Yazdani et al. (2011)	Average Pressure Tanyimboh, & Templeman (1998)	$CPI_{1,Net}$	$CPI_{2,Net}$	Awumah et al. (1990)	Todini (2000)	Jayaram and Srinivasan (2008)
Net1 L07L32MA	No reduction	0.849	1.000	1.000	1.000	0	0.997	0.476
	10	0.849	1.000	1.000	1.000	0	0.997	0.476
	20	0.849	1.000	1.000	1.000	0	0.997	0.476
	30	0.849	1.000	1.000	1.000	0	0.997	0.476
	40	0.849	1.000	1.000	1.000	0	0.997	0.476
	50	0.849	1.000	1.000	1.000	0	0.997	0.476
	60	0.849	1.000	1.000	1.000	0	0.997	0.476
	70	0.849	1.000	1.000	1.000	0	0.996	0.476
	80	0.849	1.000	1.000	1.000	0	0.991	0.476
90	0.849	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	0	0.817	0.476
Net2 AL-1194	No reduction	0.805	0.991	0.982	0.991	0.537	0.293	0.082
	10	0.805	0.991	0.982	0.991	0.537	0.293	0.082
	20	0.805	0.991	0.982	0.991	0.537	0.293	0.082
	30	0.805	0.991	0.982	0.991	0.537	0.293	0.082
	40	0.805	0.991	0.982	0.991	0.537	0.293	0.082
	50	0.805	0.991	0.982	0.991	0.537	0.293	0.082

60	0.805	0.991	0.982	0.991	0.537	0.293	0.082
70	0.805	0.991	0.982	0.991	0.537	0.293	0.082
80	0.805	0.991	0.982	0.991	0.537	0.293	0.082
90	0.805	0.991	0.354	0.003	0.537	0.000	0.000

Table 4 presents the impacts of gradual diameter reduction in critical pipes for Net1 and Net2. In Net1, a 10 to 90% reduction in the diameter of pipe-L07L32MA had no significant impact on the Critical Performance Indicators (CPIs) nor the system's vulnerability and average pressure ratio. From Table 4, Net2 showed a considerable decrease in $CPI_{1,Net}$ and $CPI_{2,Net}$ with a 90% reduction in pipe-AL-1194, the $CPI_{1,Net}$ and $CPI_{2,Net}$ decreased from 0.982 and 0.991 to 0.354 and 0.003, respectively, primarily due to increased headloss as the pipe diameter decreased. Surprisingly, this severe reduction in pipe-AL-1194's diameter did not impact the system's vulnerability (Yazdani et al., 2011) and average pressure ratio (Tanyimboh & Templeman, 1998), suggesting that these indices may not fully capture the system's response to such drastic changes.

System resilience for Net1, as measured by the Todini (2000) index, began to deteriorate slightly when the diameter of pipe L07L32MA was reduced by 80% and 90%, resulting in 1% and 22% reductions in resilience, respectively. This is compared with the original resilience of 0.997, and with Todini's (2000) index averages of 0.991 and 0.817. As Jayaram and Srinivasan (2008) suggest, their index factors in network redundancy and alternate flow paths, which specific reductions in pipe diameter may not significantly impact. Consequently, a mere reduction in pipe diameter, as opposed to a complete blockage, does not result in a substantial change in the index value. This implies that when a pipe becomes blocked, the network can reroute water through alternative paths, maintaining a certain degree of service. Observing that network resilience drops to zero with a 90% reduction in pipe diameter, but only slightly reduces with a complete blockage, provides valuable insight into the impact of pipe defects on network resilience. The network's ability to adapt to blockages, enabled by its looped structure, is a crucial factor influencing these results.

For Net2, characterised by its complex looped structure, resilience is significantly reduced when the diameter of pipe AL-1194 is reduced by 90%. The resilience indices proposed by Jayaram and Srinivasan (2008) and Todini (2000) drop to zero from 0.293 and 0.082, respectively, in Table 4. Such a reduction creates a flow bottleneck, adversely affecting the network's overall flow capacity and reducing resilience. Intriguingly, completely blocking pipe-AL-1194 resulted in only a slight decrease in the resilience index, from 0.293 to 0.082, and from 0.290 to 0.078, according to Todini (2000) and Jayaram and Srinivasan (2008), respectively. This highlights the inherent redundancy in the system's design.

In both Net1 and Net2, the entropy remained consistent despite varying degrees of diameter reduction (from 10% to 80%) in pipes L07L32MA and AL-1194 as shown in Table 4. As these pipes were only reduced, not blocked, connectivity was maintained, thereby preserving system reliability as evidenced by the stable $CPI_{1,Net}$ and $CPI_{2,Net}$ values. However, when the diameter reduction reached 90% for pipe L07L32MA in Net1, network resilience dropped from 0.997 to 0.817. Even more drastic, the same reduction for pipe AL-1194 led to a complete loss of system resilience in Net2, thereby crossing a threshold of robustness. This negatively affected customer satisfaction, as mirrored in the $CPI_{1,Net}$ and $CPI_{2,Net}$ values in Net2.

CPI_1 and CPI_2 are indices that capture customer experience across the two networks, focusing on maintaining a minimum pressure threshold of 20 meters. While CPI_1 measures the duration of the network meeting this threshold, indicating the system's reliability, CPI_2 examines the severity of pressure deficits when they occur, reflecting the network's resilience. Although both indices provide valuable insights into the network's performance, CPI_2 arguably offers a more practical assessment. CPI_2 enables a nuanced understanding of the customer experience during service disruptions by quantifying the extent of pressure deficits. This granular perspective enables targeted improvements and resource allocation, fostering a more robust and dependable WDN. By identifying not only the occurrence but also the magnitude of pressure

deficits, CPI_2 facilitates strategic network maintenance and enhancement, underscoring its superiority as a customer-oriented performance index compared to CPI_1 .

Conclusions

In this research, we examined the performance of water distribution networks (WDNs) by introducing two innovative, Customer-oriented Performance Indices: CPI_1 and CPI_2 . These indices evaluate the duration and severity of pressure deficiencies compared to a set performance pressure threshold. We juxtaposed existing hydraulic, entropy, and resilience indices to assess the system's ability to meet user demand, robustness, structural redundancy, connectivity, and resilience against unexpected supply disruptions.

Our findings underscore that a highly interconnected and robust network does not necessarily ensure minimum service-level maintenance. For instance, even with multiple water supply paths, users are not guaranteed to receive sufficient water if the primary path fails. The proposed performance indices proved to be practical tools for identifying underperforming nodes using Equations (2) and (4); we could gauge the sensitivity of each pipe precisely on nodes in the network, as shown in Figures 1 and 2, providing valuable insights into customer service levels. The CPI for individual nodes enabled us to measure both the severity and duration of pressure deficits at those nodes, which are a direct result of the defective status of the pipes. In addition, applying Equations (3) and (5), as shown in Table 5, the CPI could quantify the overall system performance of the WDN. This approach offers crucial insights into the criticality of various pipes, suggesting a more frequent inspection and maintenance schedule for these critical components. The overall CPI indices, $CPI_{1,Net}$ and $CPI_{2,Net}$, offer an index for assessing water distribution network (WDN) performance across diverse configurations, making them universally applicable across organisations and countries that uphold minimum pressure standards. By pinpointing critical pipes and gauging the impact of various defects on network performance, these indices could inform strategic investment decisions, helping water companies enhance service quality for their customers.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing commercial interests or personal relationships that could have influenced the work reported in this paper.

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